

Making robots for arts

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

KONEXinc is specialized in making robotic machines for arts. For instance, we work on dance with humanoid robots or big setup with cable driven robots in museums or dancing with drones. Doing this, we did find a lot of small innovations to help robots coming in real life, not only practically but also ethically thanks to contact with audience. Our main subject is creating robots for green development.

2. Aim

Develop robotics to improve energy efficiency in buildings thanks to artistic projects

3. Material and methods

Method is to develop machines for arts (we already did almost 20 machines) and to test very new against very old technologies. In parallel, we develop a smart home server based on innovation in arts.

4. Results

20 machines in arts

The smart home server is in development for a first release in 2018.

5. Conclusions

This kind of innovation method is very cool since each person in KONEXinc can create its own piece of art and also work for other artists. It is also an occasion to test last technologies like robotics, drones or artificial intelligence.

6. Keywords

Robot, drones, artificial intelligence, arts, smart home, art brainstorming

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Author biography

Thomas Peyruse Thomas Peyruse is automatic engineer since 2006. He worked in Astrium for spacecraft control during 2 years and in Airbus for aircraft control (A350-900) during 8 years. In parallel, he became artist as an actor and clown in several projects.

In 2015, he stopped his activities to become “the two” putting robots on stage and met the choreographer Eric Minh Cuong Castaing to make a show with humanoid robots and children.

In 2017, he created with 5 associate the company KONEXinc to follow other artistic projects and address smart home issues.